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A comprehensive description of the circulating tumor cell: DCHS1.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

The circulating tumor cell (CTC) is most likely responsible for effective metastasis (1-3). We measured total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the blood of women with stage IV breast cancer to define at the molecular level the most significant changes that accompany dissemination in a migrating tumor cell population (4) and integrated these with transcriptomic study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with metastatic prostate cancer (5). We identify here DCHS1 as a differentially expressed target in the circulating tumor cell in humans with cancer.

1 Circulating tumor cells are likely the tumor cell population that function in dissemination and do so by
2 seeding distant organ sites. We defined the CTC transcriptome, describing the most significant changes
3 by target and using normal blood cells from the peripheral blood as a control reference transcriptome.

4 **Results**

5 **Figure 1:** DCHS1 is differentially expressed in the circulating tumor cell.

6 I. CTC from humans with stage IV breast cancer (peripheral blood).

7 *n*=18 normal cells from the peripheral blood (human)

8 *n*=14 circulating tumor cells; humans with stage IV breast cancer; peripheral blood

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8642	6.01E-05	0.669	-4.0124218	-2.6831729	65.36	DCHS1	3586/21908	83.6

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10 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the
11 peripheral blood of women with stage IV breast cancer and transcription in normal cells of the blood (5),
12 we discovered differential expression of dachsous cadherin-related 1, encoded by *DCHS1* in the CTC
13 humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of DCHS1 changed more than nearly 85% of the human
14 transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 21,908
15 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of DCHS1 messenger
16 RNA in the CTC, indicating up-regulation of DCHS1 disease progression and metastasis from primary
17 tumor to CTC during the tumor life cycle.

18 Thus, differential and increased expression of DCHS1 is a defining change of the circulating tumor
19 cell gene expression signature in humans with metastatic breast cancer.

20 **Discussion**

21 We provided evidence here that DCHS1 is a molecular target of modulation in the CTC. This
22 included a panel of cell surface markers, some of whose expression was conserved as marking the CTC
23 in prostate cancer but of some of whose expression was specific to the circulating tumor cell in humans
24 with metastatic breast cancer.
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Methods

We utilized GSE113890 (4) for this transcriptome study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with cancer, measuring whole transcription in CTC isolated from peripheral blood from humans with stage IV breast cancer, as compared to normal cells from the peripheral blood (along with a second dataset GSE202650 (5) studying the CTC in humans with prostate cancer for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).